

STUDY OF PARENTHETICAL UNITS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. *This article discusses the problems of parenthetical units in Modern English. It gives information about general notions of parenthetical units and its development.*

Key words: *parenthetical units, semantics, grammar, speaker, syntactic category, scientists.*

The study of parentheses in Russian linguistics began in the first half of the 19th century. Russian linguists of that time studied this phenomenon under the name of "introductions" within the framework of the rule of using punctuation marks without distinguishing them from introductions. The first ideas about parentheses in Uzbek linguistics were expressed in the works of a number of scientists such as A. Zahiri, Fitrat, K. Ramazan, H. Goziyev at the beginning of the last century. The fact that introductions and introductions are different syntactic categories was first established by A. Gulomov in Turkic studies. One of the recent studies on introductions in the Uzbek language is the candidate's dissertation of I. Toshaliyev on the topic "Introduction constructions in the modern Uzbek literary language".

In the process of speech communication, the units of all language levels come into action, and this highest coordinator of these actions is communicative syntax. As a result, the sentence and the text, which are the main units of speech communication, are formed on the basis of these rules of communicative syntax. Communicative syntax always refers to the relations between the speaker, the listener, and speech, as well as the peculiarities of these relations. Of course, the semantic structure and system are formed based on the rules of syntax. Communicative syntax always refers to the relations between the speaker, the listener, and the speech, as well as the peculiarities of those relations. pays the main attention to the processes of speech realization of the rules and considers them as the main task of learning [1].

As I. Toshaliyev, one of the serious researchers of the problems of syntax and stylistics of the Uzbek language, rightly mentioned, "linguistic changes are considered in

terms of differences between language and speech, language system and speech activity, general and stability and randomness." can also be interpreted. Determining the boundary between systemic linguistics and communicative linguistics is also based on these principles. It should be noted that system linguistics and communicative linguistics complement each other in terms of linguistic usage. The size, structure, modal-communicative, artistic-aesthetic aspects of the sentence (or text) may be different according to the needs and requirements of the corresponding speech communication. In accordance with this need and demand, in the speech process, the sentence is condensed, expanded, increases the content capacity while maintaining its usual form, includes various additional information, and reflects the changes in the attitude of the speaker to the expressed opinion in different degrees. , otherwise, there are many different phenomena, such as the specific poetic emphasis of a word or a certain part, which occurs through different syntactic methods and devices. For example, with the introduction of second-order predicate constructions into a simple sentence, the normal form of the sentence is preserved, its content capacity increases, and a form-content imbalance occurs in the sentence. These and similar laws were studied by N. Mahmudov in Uzbek linguistics. Another of these methods and tools is inputs and inputs. Such units, as well as isolated fragments, impulses, actual fragmentation, communicative types of sentences, adjunct constructions and other similar phenomena are regulated in various linguistics as rules of communicative syntax. In particular, introductions and introductions in a sentence are particularly noteworthy for their serious communicative and at the same time semantic, structural and linguopoetic value. Naturally, there

is no need to prove that introductions and inputs are the object of study of both communicative syntax and constructive syntax [2].

At this point, first of all, it is appropriate to dwell on the terms representing these units. In most linguistics such units, the term "parenthesis" or "parenthesis" has traditionally been used in German grammars to represent both introductory and input units. This situation is also observed in the works of Belarusian, Russian and other linguists devoted to the problems of the German and English languages. V. G. Admoni, a major researcher of German grammar, writes: An introductory construction (parentheses) is usually understood as a sentence inserted into another sentence (introductory containing) without any formal grammatical connections. The semantic relationship between a parenthesis and an introductory sentence is extremely diverse. As can be understood from this idea, the scientist meant by the term "parentheses" a unit included in another sentence without certain formal-grammatical connections, in particular, both introductions and introductions. Undoubtedly, he emphasizes the great variety of meaningful relations between the parenthesis and the main introductory sentence, and emphasizes the semantic-functional differences between introductions and introductions, as well as the substantive aspects specific to each of them. Some Russian linguists prefer the term "parenthesis" rather than "parenthesis" as a general name for introductions and entries. And some linguists try to give some terminological meaning to these two phonetic forms of this term. For example, L.G. Khatiashvili, who has been researching the same problem in the syntax of the Russian language for a long time (in 1953 he defended his candidate's thesis in Tbilisi on the topic "Introductory sentences in the modern Russian literary language"), in his article entitled "Parenthesis and text" published on the Internet, writes: "denotes an input syntactic event, so the input constructions are called "parenthetical constructions". The term "parenthesis" denotes an input syntactic event, so the input constructions are called "parenthetical constructions" [3].

In our opinion, it is inappropriate to choose two phonetic variants of the same word as

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different terms for two syntactic events, because it will not be possible to express the essence of the events in this way. In addition, introductions and generalizations tend to avoid the term "parentheses" or "parentheses", which are traditionally used in linguistics to refer to various introductions. However, the word parenthesis (parentheses) fully justifies itself as a term that can correctly and accurately express the essence of inputs and inputs. The word is actually the Greek parenthesis, which means "introduction." The same word parenthesis has been adopted into the French language as parentheses and is used to express the meanings of "introductory word" and "bracket". The word parentheses(a) is used in Russian as a typographical term meaning "figure bracket" in addition to its linguistic meaning. This word is used only as the name of parenthetical punctuation in modern Turkish. French rhetoricians call the clauses or other units enclosed in parentheses in the sentence parentheses. Russian linguist N.D. Arutyunova uses the terms "parenthetical position" and "parenthetical function" to express that this or that unit comes as an input (or input) part in the positional structure of the sentence and performs such a task [4].

It is clear from the above that the term "parentheses" (which we, like a number of other linguists, prefer. D.J.) means "introduction, introduction" and "separation by parentheses (or other punctuation marks)". Indeed, the positional-structural nature of both introductions and introductions in the sentence is that both of them are included in the main sentence from the outside. At the same time, intonation is distinguished within the main clause, and this distinction is indicated in the writing by parentheses or other appropriate punctuation marks. Linguists pay serious attention to this aspect of this phenomenon, and probably for this reason, in most cases, they allocate a special place to the description of introductions and introductions in the part of linguistics about punctuation. It should also be said that terms other than "parentheses // parentheses" are used in various linguistics as general names for introductions and inputs. For example, some researchers in Russian linguistics use the term "Vstavka" (introduction). A.F. Priyatkina names

both of these syntactic phenomena with the term "insertion" (introduction), regardless of the content of the word, phrase, sentence or larger constructional units involved in the complexity of the sentence. And A.A.Reformatsky, summarizing not only inputs and inputs, but also impulses together with them, applies the term "vnesenie" (Kyrgyz) to them. Inputs and inputs, as well as other units close to them in terms of position and structure, are called "vklinenie" in the syntactic concept put forward by I.F. Vardul. " (break Kyrgyzma, squeeze Kyrgyzma). L.G. Vedenina, who studied the problem of sentences in the French language, also uses the same term, calls the breaking of one sentence into another "vklinenie" and emphasizes that it is a text-forming method. In Turkish linguistics, there is no specific compact term for introductions and introductions, as well as syntactic units that do not have a direct syntactic connection with sentence fragments (in particular, with part of a sentence) and are inserted into the sentence from the outside, therefore such units are called "extra-sentence elements" (" is named by a descriptive expression in the style of "sentential elements".

In Uzbek linguistics, there is no specific generalizing term for introductions and introductions. In fact, the word "introduction" can be used as a general term, which can represent the phenomenon of introducing another unit into the positional-structural composition of the sentence. But in our linguistics, this word is used to express a syntactic phenomenon that contradicts introductions and entered the scientific tradition. Taking this into account, we consider it appropriate to use the terms "parentheses" and "parentheses units" in Uzbek as a term that summarizes introductions and inputs. Being Uzbek, parenthetical units are not a phenomenon that appeared yesterday or today in our language, of course. However, I. Toshaliyev, who was one of the first to thoroughly study introductory constructions in linguistics and Turkic studies in general, interprets them as a new phenomenon in our language in his candidate's thesis. He writes: "New forms of syntactic constructions have appeared in the Uzbek language: the possibilities of internal means, the scope of their use have expanded, they have become more active, and various forms have appeared. The fact that

introductions and introduction constructions, motivations and other linguistic phenomena are widely used today can be a proof of this point. One such new phenomenon is input constructions [5].

Naturally, it is difficult to agree with such an opinion, because input constructions, in general, parenthetical units are characteristic of the Uzbek language from time immemorial, they did not appear under the influence of other languages. Even in the old Turkic language "introductory words and introductory sentences are used". In textbooks on the historical grammar of the Uzbek language, and in various dissertation studies, clear opinions about the use of these units and their peculiarities are stated. For example, G. Abdurakhmanov states the following: in "Kutadgu bilig" some verbs (kör, bil, kəl, etc.) often appear as introductory words... In the old Uzbek language, both the range of introductory words and the amount of use are much wider. Introductory sentences are also found in the old Turkic language... Introductory sentences are used somewhat more in the old Turkish language... In the old Uzbek language, the use of introductory sentences is somewhat expanded. S. Ashirboev, who seriously studied the structural and semantic characteristics of simple sentences in Alisher Navoi's prose works, writes: "Explanation and introduction" The use of the kim // ki tool in expressions, the use of the kim // ki tool (in the literature, it is also called a tool, a connecting tool) to indicate the presence of introductory and explanatory phrases, certainly ensures the uniqueness of the old Uzbek language. Comments and introductory phrases in the current Uzbek language are not connected to the part being explained or clarified in the sentence by means of special indicators. There is no need for it. Because in our current written language punctuation marks are used enough to indicate the grammatical relationship or separation of each syntactic event. And the old Uzbek language was devoid of such information symbols... In 44 of the sentences with comments and introductory phrases recorded in the prose works of Alisher Navoi, the tool kim // ki was used, and only 12 used them. is not an event, but a pre-existing event. Only in later periods, the scope of such units expanded, and they were not

developed in the syntactic structure of our literary language.

References

1. Begmatov E. Mamatov A. Adabiy norma nazariyasi, III qism. - Toshkent, 1998. –257 b.
2. G'apparov M, Qosimova R, “ Ingliz tili grammatikasi “ T.: -2008–265 b.
3. Haydarov Sh. “Badiiy matnda parselliyativ konstruksiyalarning qo‘llanilishi” T-2011
4. Hakimov, M. 2013. O‘zbek pragmalingvistikasi asoslari. Toshkent. –273 b.
5. Imomov K., Mirzaev T va b. O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodi. – T.: O‘qituvchi, 1990. 84-99 b.
6. Ishoqov F. “Hozirgi zamon o‘zbek tilida ilovali konstruksiyalar” Adabiyotshunoslik va tilshunoslik masalalari, 2-kitob Toshkent. O‘z Fanlar akademiyasi.
7. Jamoliddinova. “Badiiy nutqda parantez (kirish va kiritma) birliklarning grammatik va lingvopoetik xususiyatlari” –T. 2009
8. Ko‘chiboyev, A. 2015. Matn pragmatikasi. Samarqand. –457 b.
9. Mahmudov N.M. O‘zbek tilidagi sodda gaplarda semantik-sintaktik asimmetriya. – Toshkent. O‘qituvchi, 1984.
10. Mamatov A.E. Zamonaviy lingvistika. Toshkent: “Noshir” 2019. 27-41 b.

